

COVID-19 Testing Equity Through Messaging Accuracy and Accessibility

RADx-UP EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY PROGRAM EA3 Preliminary Feedback, Milestones and Next Steps

Third RADx-UP Equity Evidence Academy

Structural Overview

Community
Presenters

21

Academic
Presenters

22

- **2** nationally recognized Keynote Speakers, leaders in COVID-19 Testing Messaging
- **9** community and academic expert breakout session presenters
- **12** RADx-UP community-academic partnered project teams provided presentations (4 oral, 8 poster)
- **4** interactive opportunities offered:
 - Roundtable Discussions
 - Networking Sessions
 - Participant Profiles and 1:1 interaction features
 - Discussion Wall

Geographic Representation of Presenters

Attendee Overview – RADx-UP Affiliations and Project Types

Attendee Affiliation with RADx-UP (n=254)

Number of Projects Represented	
83	
Individual Project Representation by Type (n=149)	
Phase I	Phase II
52 (35%)	28 (19%)
Rapid Research Pilots	Return to School
11 (7%)	14 (9%)
Community Collaborations	Say Yes COVID Test Grant
5 (3%)	3 (2%)
I Don't Know	
36 (24%)	

59% of all registered attendees

*Gathered from WebEx Events Registration Data

Attendee Overview – Gender, Race, and Ethnicity (n=245)

Attendee Ethnicity Compared to US Population's Ethnicity (n=254)

Attendee Race (n=254) Compared to US Population's Race

Attendee Gender Identity (n=254)

Gender Identity	Female	Male	Queer, Nonbinary	Prefer Not To Say/No Response
EA Attendees	80%	15%	2%	3%
US Population	51%	49%	Unavailable	NA

*Gathered from WebEx Events Registration Data and United States Census Bureau 2021

Attendee Overview - Male Participants by RADx-UP Affiliation Type

Participant Affiliation with RADx-UP	Number (%) n=38
RADx-UP Project Team Academic Partner	15 (39%)
RADx-UP CDCC Staff Event Volunteers	6 (16%)
RADx-UP Project Team Community Partner	5 (13%)
RADx-UP CDCC Staff Member	5 (13%)
RADx-UP Stakeholders and Partners	5 (13%)
NIH Representative	2 (5%)

Attendee Overview – *Geographic Representation (n=245)*

Note: 38/53 states and territories are represented, including District of Columbia (4), Puerto Rico (2), and the Marshall Islands (1)

*Gathered from WebEx Events Registration Data

EA₃ Attendance by Session

Day	Session Name	# of Attendees	Average Minutes Spent Viewing Live Session / Total Session Length
Day 1	Opening Session and Keynote Address by Dr. Cameron Webb	125	62 / 75 minutes
Day 1	Breakout Sessions (Six Sessions Totaled)	126	40 / 60 minutes
Day 1	Roundtable Discussions	43	NA
Day 1	Roundtable Report Out and Day 1 Closing	71	13 / 15 minutes
Day 2	Day 2 Open: ACAP Oral Presentations	147	40 / 140 minutes
Day 2	ACAP Poster Presentation Session	31	NA
Day 2	Closing Keynote Address by Dr. Amelie Ramirez	77	31 / 35 minutes

Day 1 Feedback – Opening Keynote, Breakout Presentations and Roundtable Discussions

RADx-UP EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY

Messengers, warnings, & trust: Communicating about the vaccine on social media

Theme 1: Breakout: Social Media Messengers

MISINFORMATION LEADS TO CONFUSION + MISTRUST + SKEPTICISM
Changes in or overly medicalized info leads to faster spread

CONSPIRACY CLAIMS
MEDICAL MISINFO.
VACCINE DEVELOPMENT

DO THESE ESTABLISHED CHANNELS OF SOURCE INFO QUALITY AVOID PANIC - MEDICAL RECOMMENDATIONS TRANSPARENT

CONSPIRACY CLAIMS
CORRELATION: TRUST vaccine hesitancy
CAN USE SOCIAL MEDIA TO CORRECT MISINFORMATION

COMMUNICATION PREFERENCES
SOCIAL LISTENING
MOTIVATIONS
FEEDBACK

MESSAGE TAILORING
21% OF AMERICANS: SOCIAL MEDIA = MOST INFLUENTIAL SOURCE OF COVID-19 INFO

PEAKS OF SOCIAL MEDIA SEARCHES ON COVID-19 PRECEDE IN CASES BY 10-14 DAYS

EFFECTIVE MESSAGING
BENEFITS OF SUCCESS
CREDIBILITY
EVIDENCE-BASED
TRANSPARENT

TARGETED MESSAGING
EXAMINE TESTING BARRIERS
THE UNDERSERVED COMMUNITIES
MULTIPLE CHANNELS = EFFECTIVE

"INFODEMIC"
FAST & WIDESPREAD
DISSEMINATION OF MISINFO AND UNRELIABLE INFO

BENEFITS OF SOCIAL MEDIA
OPEN-SOURCE
RAPID
NO-COST

REPUTATIONS + PRIMARY CARE PROVIDERS AS RELIABLE SOURCES
BEYOND SOCIAL MEDIA

DR. ANTHONY HUIZ, PHD
in collaboration with JULIE GORDON, PHD

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Stop the Spread: Protege Tu Familia

Theme 2: Patients Through A Communication Lens

INTENTION: CLEAR OUR WORK TOWARDS OUR COMMUNITY
BUILT & DRIVING
ROOTED IN RESPONSE TO AIDS PANDEMIC

FAMILIA: MULTI-GENERATIONAL CAMPAIGN
OUR NAME: ENGLISH AND SPANISH SPEAKERS

WHAT DID WE LEARN?
COMMUNITY LACKS TRUST IN HEALTH INSTITUTIONS
INEQUALITY IN HEALTH RESOURCES + DISTRIBUTION OF SERVICES
HEALTH EDUCATION: LIMITED IN MARGINALIZED COMMUNITIES

COVID-19 + UNDERSERVED COMMUNITIES
UNEMPLOYMENT
HOUSING + FOOD INSECURITY
LOSS OF LOVED ONES

MENTAL HEALTH STRUGGLES
TECH + INTERNET ISSUES

LANGUAGE + LITERACY CHALLENGES
↑ IN DOMESTIC VIOLENCE
SUBSTANCE ALCOHOL USE

STIGMA
COMPROMISE OF FAMILY DYNAMICS

SPIRITUAL + COMMUNITY LIMITATIONS

HIRING KEY TRUSTED LOCAL (COMMUNITY) INFLUENCERS

CULTURALLY-COMPETENT MATERIALS

VIRTUAL TOWN HALLS WITH SPIRITUAL LEADERS + TRANSLATION

DOOR-TO-DOOR OUTREACH

PPE DISTRIBUTION

SOCIAL MEDIA TO DISTRIBUTE INFO

ENGAGE WITH CULTURALLY-RELEVANT ENTERTAINMENT

RODOLFO ZALDIVAR

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Illuminating Data: Visualizing Pandemic Response & Recovery

Theme 3: Data Visualizations

EQUITY IS BOTH A MORAL + ECONOMIC IMPERATIVE.

CONSIDER THIS:
ROUNDING
COLOR CONSIDERATIONS

ORDER OF CATEGORIES

LANGUAGE ACCESS

OUR VISION OF KNOWLEDGE
EXPERIENTIAL
CULTURAL + SPIRITUAL MAINSTREAM

ACT NOW!
INCLUDE US ALL!
WHO IS INCLUDED?
WHO ISN'T?
WHO DECIDES?

COVID DATA DASHBOARDS TO DRIVE ACTION + ADVOCACY!

WHERE DO WE FALL ON THE PARTICIPATION CONTINUUM?

COMMUNITY PARTNERSHIPS
CROSS-SECTOR SOURCES
DEMOCRATIZED, ACTIONABLE DATA
STRATEGIES

THE NARRATIVE YOU'RE TELLING STARTS WITH DATA.

USER-FRIENDLY
KNOW YOUR AUDIENCE

UNIQUE INDICATORS
NARRATIVE COMMUNITY-TESTED

DISAGGREGATED DATA
RESOURCE FOR MOVEMENTS

NARRATIVE JARGON-FREE DATA

OUR RESEARCH CAMPAIGN POLICY-DRIVEN
RIGOROUS (AS COOPERATION)
ACCESSIBLE

JENNIFER TRAN, MPA
SELENA TAN, MPA

NATIONAL EQUITY ATLAS POLICY LINK
HRC EQUITY RESEARCH INSTITUTE

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The Reservation Enemy-Killer: COVID-19 & its Lasting Effects on Montana Tribes

Theme 4: The Infodemic of Mental Health Breakout

INFRASTRUCTURE BREAKDOWN

SYSTEMIC POLICY
SOCIO-POLITICAL LEADING INDICATORS
HEALTH EQUITY

I HONOR MY UNCLE & MY BELOVED GRANDMOTHER, LOST TO COVID-19

THE DATA IS SHOWING US THE PROBLEMS - WE HAVE A CHANCE TO CORRECT THEM.

INDIAN HEALTH SERVICES
MISSING THE BOAT: INCOMPLETE + OUTDATED DATA
INCOMPLETE + OUTDATED DATA

CRISIS RECOVERY we listen.

A STORY OF MANY PANDEMICS
COVID, SUICIDE, + BEYOND...

EXCLUSION OF INDIGENOUS DATA HAS CAUSED GREAT HEALTH EQUITY HARM

LEADERSHIP SUPPORT ROLES, WE MUST ALSO LOOK + HEAL WITHIN OURSELVES

STRUCTURAL INEQUALITIES + SYSTEMIC INEQUITIES
INADEQUATE LEADERSHIP NEGATIVELY IMPACTED OUR COMMUNITIES

BRIDGING TO ATTUNE OURSELVES TO THE DISCONNECTIONS - & WORK TO MAKE AMENDS

FREE, NON-JUDGMENTAL SUPPORT

LANGUAGE MATTERS
ASK: WHAT DO YOUR COMMUNITIES WANT THE CARE?

DR. JIMMENA ANDRAGON, PHD

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Teaching Media Literacy Skills to Students for More Accurate Interpretation of Health Info

Theme 5: Health Literacy & the Interpretation of Information

INFORMATION DISORDER
MORE INCLINED TO BELIEVE SUBJECTIVE INFO THAN OBJECTIVE INFO-FO

DEEP FAKES
TODAY'S ISSUES

DISCERN PRESSING ISSUES
EXPLORE BIASES

ACTIVE, OPEN-MINDED THINKING

WE MUST WORK TOGETHER TO COMBAT AND IDENTIFY MISINFORMATION

THERE IS A NEED FOR MEDIA LITERACY NOW MORE THAN EVER

CONFIRMATION BIAS
RESULTS IN ECHO CHAMBERS THROUGH TARGETED ALGORITHMS

CLICKBAIT

PROPAGANDA
CREDIBLE, FACTUAL

MISDISSEM. INFORMATION (MDMI)

ACCESS
ANALYZE
EVALUATE
CREATE
ACT

WE MUST WORK TOGETHER TO COMBAT AND IDENTIFY MISINFORMATION

TRUST ME

FACT-CHECKING LITERACY RESOURCES
AD FONT'S MEDIA DIAL CHART
CYBER CITIZENSHIP INITIATIVE
MULTIPLE SOURCES!
FACT-CHECK.ORG
TEACHING MEDIA LITERACY (BOOK)

INTERVIEW: 5 TIPS TO SPOT MISINFORMATION

SHARE RESOURCES
CENTER YOUTH INTEREST
SAFE DIALOGIC SPACE

TRUST ME

FACT-CHECK.ORG
TEACHING MEDIA LITERACY (BOOK)

POWER LINES (BOOK)
SNOOPES
LATERAL READING
FIELD GUIDES
MEDIA LITERACY IN ACTION (BOOK)
LIBRARIES

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Planting the Roots of Equity through Grassroots Work: Making COVID-19 Safety Accessible to Farmworkers

Theme 6: Information Accessibility

CHALLENGES
EXTRACTIVE FOOD SYSTEM
EXCLUDED FROM LABOR LAWS
WORKING + LIVING CONDITIONS
LACK OF TRANSPORTATION
PAID BY PRODUCTION (QUOTAS)

TAKING ACTION INSPIRED BY OUR RIGHTFUL ANGER

WE KNOW HELP WOULDN'T COME, OR IT WOULD BE VERY SLOW SO THAT FORCED US TO TAKE ACTION, EVEN PUTTING OUR LIVES ON THE LINE

AS RESEARCHERS: BE SURE TO ASK ABOUT PEOPLE'S JOBS - TO DRAW CONNECTIONS

COVID + FARMWORKERS
NO HEALTH INSURANCE
FEW HEALTH CENTERS, LONG-TERM HEALTH EFFECTS
VULNERABLE WORKERS (IMMIGRANTS, W/AS, LANGUAGED)

COMMUNITY ORGANIZING BECAME "LIVES"

POLITICAL ATTACKS
UNCERTAINTY
THE U.S. WAS BUILT + CONTINUES TO BE RUN ON AN EXPLOITED WORK FORCE

MUTUAL AID + FUNDING
POP-UP CLINICS
COMMUNITY EVENTS
MEDIA OUTREACH IN RURAL AREAS
COLLABORATIONS, POLICIES + LEGAL ACTION

COMMUNITY ORGANIZING BECAME "LIVES"

STRATEGIES
OUTREACH IN RURAL AREAS

EDGAR FRANKS, MD
NEHA KALCHOURI, MA

TRUST ME

FACT-CHECKING LITERACY RESOURCES
AD FONT'S MEDIA DIAL CHART
CYBER CITIZENSHIP INITIATIVE
MULTIPLE SOURCES!
FACT-CHECK.ORG
TEACHING MEDIA LITERACY (BOOK)

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LATERAL READING
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MEDIA LITERACY IN ACTION (BOOK)
LIBRARIES

ART BY: A VISUAL APPROACH

Day 1 Feedback: Breakout Sessions and Opening Keynote

Day 1 Attendees

160 Unique Attendees

Post-Event

46 Session Views

Positive Feedback

Constructive Criticism

The breakout session went very smoothly and felt very intimate. Ample time was given to Q&A.

I forgot to register in advance and had trouble accessing some of the sessions on day 1

Very organized, helpful visuals and examples

*The speaker was very engaging and lively. **She really rolled with the punches as there were technical difficulties.** I thought her presentation was informative and she provided great resources, based on requests from the attendees.*

The presenter is extremely comprehensive and provided great insight into how cultural practices impact access to care. – Represented LGBTQ+ Communities

Presentation included a lot of material and findings from research. Was well organized and very clear

The passion of the presenter and the presenter touching on the topic of how the Native American communities has been impacted and, in a sense, forgotten during the COVID-19 pandemic. I love that he is using his voice to break generational curses and to advocate for his community.

Day 1 Feedback: Roundtable Discussions Session

Day 1 Attendees

160 Unique Attendees

Roundtable Attendees

46 Unique Attendees

*not including volunteers and staff

- Roundtables well received by attendees who successfully navigated to their assigned room and participated in rooms with several attendees
- Many participants experienced confusion locating their assigned rooms:
 - Some inadvertently saw multiple room options rather than just their assigned room due to technical platform errors
 - Some navigated to their room early and before the volunteer facilitators, leading them to believe they were not in the right 'place'
- **Lessons Learned:**
 - Use Zoom, a more familiar platform, to host small group discussions
 - Plan for attrition from registration to attendance
 - Remove the assignment process – open selection

Day 2 Feedback - Advancing Community-Academic Partnerships (ACAP) Presentation Series and Closing Keynote

RADx-UP EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY

THESE EFFORTS ALSO BUILT LONG-TERM RELATIONSHIPS:

- HUMILITY IS A KEY
- PROMOTE UNDERSTANDING
- FAITH-BASED PARTNERSHIPS + AMBASSADORS
- ENSURE TRUST
- 360° SERVICES
- LISTEN + INFORM

TRUST = TRANSPARENCY + RECIPROCALITY

FIGHT COVID MILWAUKEE: PARTNERSHIPS FOR TRUSTED MESSAGING & COMMUNITY-ENGAGED RESEARCH

BE CURIOUS???

WE PAY, PRAY, & PLAY IN THIS COMMUNITY. IT'S RELEVANT FOR US TO COME TOGETHER TO MITIGATE COVID.

ANTIBODY TEST SHOW VACCINE EFFICACY

COVID-19

OUTREACH PHOTOS THAT REPRESENT WHO WE WANT TO REACH

LOKAI IS THE ESSENCE OF UNITY & HARMONY. THESE VALUES ALIGN TO PROMOTE OVERALL HEALTH + WELL-BEING.

FQHCs + RESEARCH ADVISORY GROUP + UNIVERSITY OF HAWAII RESEARCHERS

- FUNDS SPLIT EVENLY
- REVIEW + APPROVAL BY ALL

COMMUNITY-DRIVEN APPROACH TO MITIGATE COVID DISPARITIES HAWAII PACIFIC ALLIANCE AGAINST COVID-19

YOUTH-LED ENGAGEMENT → WHAT DO STUDENTS/SCHOOLS NEED?

TRAINING + WORK EXPERIENCE

DISSEMINATE RESULTS

LONG-TERM INFRASTRUCTURE STRENGTHENING

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

EQUIPMENT AND TRAINING = ↑ CAPACITY AND TURNAROUND FOR TEST RESULTS

MULTI-GENERATIONAL

> 5,000 PEOPLE

> 16,000 TESTS

TWEAK OVER TIME

SAFE RETURNS TO SCHOOLS

"with"

INFORMED DECISIONS BASED ON FACTS

STUDENTS HEALTHY & IN SCHOOLS!

NO JUDGMENT

CULTURAL DEFICIT APPROACH

↳ VICTIM BLAMING

WE THE LION MASCOT-ENGAGING & FUN

TOWN HALLS

- PROACTIVE
- TRANSPARENT
- TRUSTED SOURCES

NO-COST TESTING AT SCHOOLS

ST. LOUIS COMMUNITY

WE HAD TO HONOR & HOLD THE HISTORICAL CONTEXT IN OUR COMMUNITY.

STRENGTH-BASED APPROACH:

- ASSET-DRIVEN
- SUPPORT SYSTEMS
- RACE + CULTURE LENS
- INTERSECTIONAL
- BI-DIRECTIONAL

AMBASSADORS

- PERSONALIZED
- RELATIONSHIP-CENTERED

ACKNOWLEDGE HARM. REPAIR TRUST.

ANCHOR

MEET PEOPLE WHERE THEY ARE = CRUCIAL.

HIGHLIGHT HUMANITY

SHARED TRUST + RESPONSIBILITY.

MUTUAL RESPECT. COMMUNICATION.

EVEN THE BEST-LAID PLANS, SOMETIMES FALL THROUGH WE OFTEN HAD TO PIVOT.

TAILORED EDUCATION SCALES = MORE EFFECTIVE

SSP-COVID TESTING

MOTIVATIONAL INTERVIEWING

HARM REDUCTION COALITION

- WRAP-AROUND HEALTH NEEDS

PEOPLE WHO INJECT DRUGS

- VULNERABLE TO SEVERE DISEASE
- LOW RATES OF TESTING + VACCINATION
- STIGMA + BARRIERS + DISTRUST
- SYRINGE SERVICE PROGRAMS = TRUSTED

LESSONS FROM THE LINK-UP COMMUNITY-ACADEMIC PARTNERSHIP TO INCREASE COVID TESTING AMONG PEOPLE WHO INJECT DRUGS IN SAN DIEGO, CA

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Day 2 Feedback - ACAP Oral Presentations by Four RADx-UP Project Teams

Day 2 Attendees

168 Unique Attendees

Post-Event

184 Session Views

Positive Feedback

*I enjoyed learning about the RADx-UP projects, the vulnerable populations that they serve, and the **methods/processes that the partnerships used to build trust in order to test and screen the different communities.***

*Getting **new ideas** from those conducting projects with similar aims*

*Great to see other **examples of community engagement** on other sectors like education*

*Getting **new ideas** from those conducting projects with similar aims*

Constructive Criticism

*Community engagement strategies. **Also zoom is so much easier vs. the other platform.***

Day 2 Feedback - ACAP Poster Presentations and Virtual Poster Booths

Unique Visitors to Poster Booths

67 Unique Visitors

Engagement in Additional Content

53 Clicks to Content

Participants in Day 2 Poster Session

39 Unique Participants

Positive Feedback

The posters were not too busy, they were short and to-the-point which is easy to read and understand. It was great to see what other projects are doing.

I like that they were available for more time than just the two days of the conference.

I learned from the poster creator, had a chance to ask questions.

I enjoyed the diversity of the exemplars.

Nice examples of community partnerships & gave me ideas of how we will present our project in the future.

Constructive Criticism

*I was a poster presenter. I liked seeing the content and community engagement approaches on other posters. **It would have been nice to have more participants join our poster session during the live portion. I think the platform made it confusing to find and know to enter the poster booth.***

Overall Platform Feedback

Positive Feedback	Constructive Criticism
<i>The [platform's] presentation of content was easy to access and understand. It made learning fun!</i>	<i>The platform was a bit confusing. Send additional instructions to access.</i>
<i>The platform functionality was great.</i>	<i>There was some initial set up issues for the platform so additional reminders to make it clear to test beforehand.</i>
<i>The platform worked well...no tech issues</i>	<i>Difficulties navigating the roundtables</i>
<i>I liked seeing participant profiles and connecting with them.</i>	<i>The platform is powerful, but complex.</i>

EA3 Recent & Upcoming Milestones

- ❖ **9.14:** EA3 Data Profile published in English and Spanish in a new format
- ❖ **9.28 & 9.29:** EA3 Event
- ❖ **9.30:** All EA3 content including session recordings and slide decks publicly available online
- ❖ **11.21:** Publish EA3 Summary Report & Community Dissemination Guide
(2-page content overview) published in English using the same interactive format as Data Profile
- ❖ **12.1:** EA3 survey results and qualitative interviews analyzed and summarized by Abacus

EA₄ Planning SWOT Analysis

SWOT	
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Initial feedback shares a clear path for improvement (using platform with Zoom as primary streaming host)• ACAP oral and poster sessions were well-received and had high engagement from project teams
Weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Persistent challenges weaving small group discussion into large virtual conference• Target audience's range in comfort level with technology is diverse, making it difficult to tailor programming to attendees' needs
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Further evaluation analysis will reveal specific ways to expand upon networking features and ACAP presentations
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Competing with target audience's limited time and multiple priorities• Communication opportunities about EA₄ to target audience is limited/easily missed due to other important messages RADx-UP must share with same audience

EA₄ Initial Ideas

- ❖ **Day 1: Conduct the 2nd Advancing Community and Academic Partnerships (ACAP) Series**
 - ❖ Emphasis on community engagement methods on two cross-cutting themes from all three prior EAs: *communication and trustworthiness*
 - ❖ Goal would be to identify common engagement methods in these two areas that could be replicated across the RADx-UP community
 - ❖ Oral presentations after an opening keynote
- ❖ **Day 2: Focus on RADx-UP project dissemination and policy** More opportunities for local/regional/national action planning
 - ❖ Report outs followed by a closing keynote

*COVID-19 Testing Equity Through
Messaging Accuracy and
Accessibility*

THANK YOU!

Feedback and Questions